
MATERIALISM AMONG MALES AND FEMALES

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to determine the Materialistic behaviour among Male and Female. Total of 60 people participated voluntarily for this purpose, their average age was 23. There are now 60 responses, 30 from Males and 30 from Females, all belong to the age criteria of 18-28 years. In this study we employ a psychological instrument in the form of THE MATERIAL VALUE SCALE by Richins, M. L.; Dawson (2004). Analysis includes the calculation of mean, standard deviations and t-value of each group {males & females}. The obtained p value is 0.64 (>0.05) shows the test is statistically not significant. The mean value of male and female are 27.27 & 26.43 respectively, hence we can say that Males are slightly more Materialistic than those of the Females. But still the difference is not significant.

KEYWORDS – Materialistic behaviour, money, happiness.

INTRODUCTION

(Happiness Outside)

“When you lose your desire for things that do not matter, you will be free.” So are we in any kind of prison? Yes, in today’s world we all human beings are trapped somewhere in the jails of materialistic desires. What are these materialistic desires and what are the causes or instigating factors for such desires? And how these differ among Male and Female? This is what we’re going to find in this study.

Materialism is defined as “the importance ascribed to the ownership and acquisitions of material goods in achieving major life goals or desired states” (Richins, 2004, p.210). The concept of materialism was first proposed by Belk (1984; 1985), who associated materialism with undesirable personal traits such as non-generosity, greed and envy, which were negatively correlated with happiness and life satisfaction.

According to Knox College Psychologist (Tim Kasser) materialists lead unhappier life and are worse to people around them. And it seems that social media might be fuelling materialistic attitudes, too.

Causes of Materialistic Behaviour – But what motivates materialistic behaviour in a person. Some research shows that there are two main sets of factors that lead people to have materialistic values:

- First, when people are more exposed to the message that material possession is what defines you or that having material possession is important to be accepted in a society one is living.
- Second, and somewhat less obvious reason is that people show more materialistic value when they are insecure or threatened, whether because of rejection or economic fears.

People who live a materialistic lifestyle will seek happiness with the possession of goods and assets. These people will not develop close relationships with others in times of hardship, nor will they resort to religion. Instead, they will purchase in an attempt to self-soothe or increase their happiness.’ They look for happiness in the material not among their friends and families.

While happiness can be achieved through purchasing precious goods, the intention behind the purchase is instrumental in determining true happiness. Materialism can also be negative if the purchasing pattern exceeds the income of the individual.

This habit can cause financial issues as well as clashes between the partners or the families regarding the expenditure or the expenses.

OBJECTIVE

- To understand the meaning and causes of materialistic behaviour among us
- To see which gender i.e. Male or Female, shows more materialistic behaviour.

MATERIAL & METHADODOLOGY

A total of 60 individuals, 30 Males and 30 Females volunteered to participate in this study. Individuals from different parts of the country were given this questionnaire to study and fill out . The age criteria for this study was 18 - 28 years and the median age was 23.

The Richins, M. L. ; Dawson (2004). The material values scale; Measurement properties and development of a short form. Journal of Consumer Research, 31, 209-219. Was used for this study. It is a 5 point Likert – scale which comprises of following options:-

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.

RESEARCH DESIGN

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Materialism is not an inborn characteristic or something that we inherit from our parents, but it is something that we learn through our experiences or sometimes as a coping mechanism.

Table 1 (Group Statistics)

Group	N	Mean	SD	Variance
Males	30	27.27	6.93	47.96
Females	30	26.43	7.1	50.42

The mean value obtained for Males is 27.27 and for Females is 26.43, so we can say that Males are slightly more Materialistic as compared to the Females. But the difference is not very significant.

Table 2 (Independent sample test)

	Levene's test for equality Of Variance		T- test for equality Of Variance	
	F	Sig	t	dF
Equal variance assumed	0.12671	0.72	0.45	58
Equal variance not assumed			0.45	57

The f- ratio obtained is 0.12671. The result is not significant hence the requirement of homogeneity is met.

Table 3 (Independent sample test)

	t-test for equality of Means			
	One sided P	Two-sided P	Mean diff.	St. Error diff.
Equal variance assumed	0.3217	0.6485	0.83	1.811
Equal variance not assumed	0.3217	0.6485	0.83	1.811

Table 4 (Independent sample test)

	t-test for equality of Means	
	Lower	Upper
Equal variance assumed	-2.7959	-4.4559
Equal variance not assumed	-2.7973	-4.4573

A total of 60 people's responses were included in this study. They were equally split in two groups i.e. Males and Females with each group consisting of 30 individuals. We then obtained the Mean, standard deviation, standard error and the t-test value. The average age for this study was 23. Results obtained shows that average for Males is 27.27 and average for Females is 26.43 . The t-test obtained t value is 0.45 and SD for Males & Females is 6.43 & 7.1 respectively . The p value is 0.64 (>0.05) and it shows that the test is not significant.

CONCLUSION

To measure Materialism in Male and Female we used the Richins, M. L. ; Dawson (2004). The material values scale. Total 60 individuals participated voluntarily for this study. 30 of them are Male and 30 are Female. The mean scores for Male and Female are 27.37 & 26.43 respectively. SD for Male and Female is 6.43 & 7.1 respectively. There is no significant difference with a t-value of 0.45. Hence, we can say that Male shows slightly high or almost similar materialistic behaviour as the Female.

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